

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

AIR-COOLED TURNING TOOL FOR AUTOMATED PROCESSES

Liberman Y.,

*Associate Professor of the Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology, Machine tools and tools
Ural Federal University named after the first President of Russia B.N. Yeltsin*

Lukinskikh S.,

*Associate Professor of the Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology, Machine tools and tools
Ural Federal University named after the first President of Russia B.N. Yeltsin*

Musina D.

*Undergraduate of the Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology, Machine tools and tools
Ural Federal University named after the first President of Russia B.N. Yeltsin*

Abstract

The article deals with the problems of insufficiently automated processes within the framework of the integrated automation of machine-building production, specifically the operations of removal and disposal of waste, in particular metal chips generated during turning. A line of cutters with internal cooling by compressed air has been developed. Such cutters make it possible to significantly simplify automation of chip removal and disposal operations by eliminating the use of cutting fluids.

Keywords: automation, metal cutting, heat sink, cutter, modeling, analysis, cooling, compressed air.

Introduction

It is well known that production automation is most effective when the automation solutions are comprehensive [1-3]. In mechanical engineering, tasks such as cutting using automatic machine tools and transport operations performed by automatic conveyors, storage and handling devices are quite fully automated today.

Meanwhile, the operations of removal and disposal of waste, in particular metal chips, usually remain insufficiently automated. This is due to the fact that high-speed cutting, inherent in automated production, as a rule, requires a particularly high resistance of the cutting tool [4-6], and cutting fluids (coolants) are usually used to increase it.

Modern coolants can be toxic to people as they evaporate, as well as a result of direct contact with the skin or contact through work clothing [7,8]. Currently, in order to improve the environmental safety of metalworking, new grades of coolant are being developed, in which toxic components are replaced by less harmful ones. However, new environmentally friendly brands are not without negative medical and biological properties. Another significant disadvantage of using coolant is the need to clean chips from it before disposal: the procedure for cleaning metal chips is quite complicated and results in additional costs [9, 10].

In connection with the above, in recent years air jet cooling has been increasingly used as a means of cooling the tool instead of using such liquids. As a rule, the air jet is directed to the front or back surface of the tool, as close as possible to the cutting blade [11-13]. The cooling effect is achieved, but the chips are widely scattered and their removal is extremely difficult.

Development of the design of a turning tool with internal air cooling

To prevent chip scattering, the Ural Federal University has developed a number of turning tools with internal cooling. One of the first rational options is a cutter [14], shown in fig. 1.

It consists of a hollow holder with a cutting insert mechanically fastened to it, under which a heat-conducting copper insert is located. At the back end of the holder there is a fitting for supplying compressed air. A copper tube is attached to the fitting, passing with a gap along the cavity of the holder. The surface of the cavity is coated with a copper coating connected to the insert.

Air is supplied to the central opening of the fitting, and exits to the atmosphere through the openings located along the perimeter of the fitting. The overall dimensions of the holder are 38x38x170, chosen due to being the most common.

Fig. 1. The developed design of the cutter with internal air cooling: 1 – hollow holder; 2 - working element; 3 – heat-conducting insert with heat-conducting coating; 4 - fitting for supplying compressed air; 5 - conical tube; a - Laval nozzle; b - air outlet holes.

To determine the effectiveness of this cutter design, we conducted a special study [15]. It was deter-

mined that with a steady thermal load of 17 watts applied to the tip of the cutter with compressed air cooling

at a pressure of 0.6 MPa, the maximum temperature after 900 sec. turned out to be 314 degrees less than under the same initial conditions in the cutter of the basic design (without cooling).

Thus, the general effectiveness of the new cutter was confirmed. However, the following remained unclear:

- what should be the dimensions of the holder cavity;
- what should be the thickness of the copper coating;
- what is the most rational design of the tube mounted in the cavity of the holder.

In order to further improve the design of the developed cutter, we studied the influence of the listed parameters on heat removal when working with a cutter of the described design to determine their optimal values in order to achieve maximum heat removal.

Research methodology

The study was conducted using SolidWorks Simulation system to model and analyze the heat transfer process during cutting.

The preparation and analysis steps were as follows.

1. Creation of a cutter design model to be studied.
2. Determination of the list and limits of change in the design parameters of the cutter during the study, the magnitude of the applied thermal load, the initial and boundary conditions of the study.
3. Planning a computer experiment and the choice of practical combinations of design parameters of the cutter to be investigated.
4. Performing heat transfer analysis in the cutter model or selected combinations of parameters and visualizing it using graphs of the dependence of the distribution of thermal energy over time.
5. Determination of the design parameters of the cutter that would provide the best dependence of the distribution of thermal energy on time (the best heat transfer from the tip of the cutter).
6. Development of measures for further modernization of the cutter design, based on the best dependence found in paragraph 5 and their analysis, similar to that indicated in paragraph 4.
7. Selection and evaluation of the most appropriate modernization option.

Table 1 shows the accepted ranges of variation of the geometric parameters indicated in fig. 1.

Table 1.

Variable parameter		A	B	C	D	E	F
Value, mm	Min	85	20	10	5	2	85
	Max	125	28	18	8	5	125

The thermal load W applied to the cutting edge and the pressure of the supplied compressed air were assumed to be the same as in [6]: 17 W and 0.6 MPa, respectively.

The plan of the experiment, formed on the basis of the selected parameters and their limits, is shown in fig. 2. It was built in accordance with the recommendations [16] and is a six-factor combination square, which made

it possible, with five levels of each factor, instead of $5^6=15626$ experiments, to perform the necessary study in just 25. If we choose experiments with the most acceptable combinations from the point of view of practical implementation options for design parameters (in Fig. 2 they are indicated by darker squares than the rest), then the number of experiments can be reduced to 14.

Fig. 2. Experiment plan

Conducting the experiment and the results

The experiment was carried out in two modules integrated into SOLIDWORKS: SOLIDWORKS Flow Simulation and SOLIDWORKS Simulation, which made it possible to predict the behavior of the product in a real environment by virtual testing CAD models.

The temperature of the cutter tip was determined in the time interval of 900 sec. in several stages:

- modeling in Flow Simulation of thermal flows of compressed air when it is supplied through a fitting and export of the obtained data to Simulation;
- thermal analysis taking into account the results of Flow Simulation and applied loads specified directly in Simulation;
- obtaining curves of dependences of temperature on time with increments of 10 and 100 seconds.

Based on the data obtained during the experiments, graphs of the dependence of the temperature of the tip of the cutter on time were plotted (Fig. 3).

The figure shows that the best result was obtained in experiment No. 5. It corresponds to $A = 126$ mm, $F = 125$ mm, $B = 28$ mm, $C = 10$ mm, $D = 8$ mm, $E = 5$ mm. With such design parameters of the cutter, the temperature of the cutter tip drops to 686°C in 900 seconds (35 degrees lower than that of the cutter shown in Fig. 1). This result was obtained after making a structural change in the model under study, namely, replacing the cylindrical hole in the tube with a conical one, having the largest diameter of 8 mm in the plane of attachment to the fitting, and the smallest diameter of 5 mm at the free end of the tube.

Fig. 3. Graphs of change in the temperature of the tip of the cutter over time.

Assuming that the determined best option may not absolutely accurate, we checked whether maintaining the determined ratio of D and E at their other values would be as or more effective. Since this ratio is approximately equal to 2, dimensions with the same ratio were tested, close to the original version: option 1 - $D = 8$, $E = 5$, which corresponds to experiment No. 5; option 2 -

$D = 6$, $E = 3$; option 3 - $D = 7$, $E = 3.5$. The results are presented in fig. 4.

It follows from the obtained results that the refined solution corresponds to $D = 7$, $E = 3.5$. The final temperature of variant 3 corresponds to 683°C : the temperature decrease in this case is no longer 35°C , but 38°C . Thus, a slight change in the inlet and outlet diameters of the conical tube made it possible to gain 3 degrees.

Fig. 4. Graphs of the change in the temperature of the cutter tip with the ratios of the parameters D and E close to the obtained best variant.

The narrowing of the diameter in the tube causes the air flow to accelerate, thereby lowering the temperature. To further increase the air flow rate after exiting the conical hole, additional changes were made to the design of the cutter:

- increased outer diameter of the end of the tube on a length of 5 mm to the size of the hole in the cavity of the holder;
- slots are made on the resulting cylindrical belt, dividing the space between the tube and the heat-conducting insert into sectors.

For two design options with slots at the end of the tube, curves of temperature change over time were determined (Fig. 5): with three slots - curve 1 and with six slots - curve 2.

Such a constructive solution, on the one hand, provides additional heat transfer due to the contact of the copper coating and the tube, and on the other hand, the slots serve as another means of accelerating the air flow from the tube, leading to an increase in heat removal. The second option turned out to be more effective. It provided a decrease in temperature to 681°C.

Fig. 5. Graphs of the change in the temperature of the cutter tip for designs with slots.

Considering the best result described above, which was due to the acceleration of the air flow along the length of the tube, it is possible to make a further improvement in the design of the cutter, based on even greater acceleration of the flow, for example, using a Laval nozzle. To do that, we determined the best geometric characteristics of the Laval nozzle based on the

results of the studies (Fig. 6): the diameter of the outlet section is 3.5 mm, the angle of the tapering shell is 40° , the angle of the expanding shell is 10.5° , the diameter of the inlet section is 3.8 mm. Dimensions of slots at the end of the tube: number of slots - 6, width - 2.5 mm, length - 5 mm, diameter of the ledge circle - 12 mm.

Fig. 6. Laval nozzle

The introduced design changes made it possible to reduce the maximum temperature of the cutter tip under the given heating conditions by 356°C - from 1035°C to 679°C (Fig. 7) compared to the cutter without internal cooling, and by 42°C - from 721°C to 679°C compared to the original design option. In addition, after reaching the maximum temperature of 679°C for ~ 40 sec. the latest design of the cutter (Fig. 8), unlike the previous

versions, provides a further decrease in temperature - up to 663°C after 900 sec. work.

A more significant decrease in temperature compared to the prototype cutter occurs due to the fact that the air jet accelerates three times when moving: passing through the conical tube, then when passing through the Laval nozzle and, finally, when passing through the slots at the end of the tube.

Fig. 7. Graph of the change in the temperature of the tip of the improved cutter design.

Fig. 8. Advanced Cutter Design: 1 – hollow holder; 2 - working element; 3 – heat-conducting insert with heat-conducting coating; 4 - fitting for supplying compressed air; 5 - conical tube; a - Laval nozzle; b - air outlet holes.

It should be noted that another positive feature of the improved design of the cutter is that both ends of the tube are fixed, resulting in increased rigidity.

This is evidenced by the conducted frequency studies in SolidWorks Simulation of the tube of the original cutter, shown in fig. 1, with one free end of the

tube, and the cutter tube with both ends fixed. In the course of these studies and calculations, according to the method described in [17], graphs of the distribution of the rigidity of the tube along its length were plotted (Fig. 9) and 5 natural frequencies of the tubes of each cutter were determined (Table 2).

Fig. 9. The distribution of the stiffness of the tube along its length in the original (1) and improved (2) incisors.

Frequency number		1	2	3	4	5
Frequency, Hz	Original cutter	447	450	2746	2764	7497
	Cutter new	1333	1334	1355	2187	2212

The table shows that the first and second natural frequencies of the new cutter have increased by almost 3 times. This result is positive, significantly expanding the possibilities of operating the cutter without the onset of resonance.

CONCLUSION

In this study, it was experimentally confirmed that internal cooling with compressed air is indeed an effective and promising means of cooling a turning tool and in many cases can be successfully used instead of traditional coolant cooling.

In the process of researching the influence of the design parameters of the cutter on the increase in heat removal, we determined that making the hole of the cutter tube conical makes it possible to improve heat removal, which results in a decrease in temperature. The slotted design of the end of the conical tube with a Laval nozzle leads to an additional decrease in temperature, and also allows to shift the range of resonant frequencies towards an increase.

The research carried out opens up quite a wide range of possibilities for using cutters with internal cooling by compressed air in automated production, since they can effectively solve the problem of automating the removal of metal chips.

References

1. Ratmirov V.A. Machine control of flexible production systems. - M.: Mashinostroenie, 1987. - 272p.
2. Flexible production systems in Japan / Per. from Japanese A.L. Semenov; Ed. L.Yu. Lishchinsky.—M.: Mashinostroenie, 1987.—232 p.
3. Flexible production complexes / Ed. P.N. Belyanin and V.A. Leshchenko.—M.: mechanical engineering, 1992. -384 p.
4. Reznikov A.N. Thermal processes in technological systems: textbook / A.N. Reznikov, L.A. Reznikov. - M.: Mechanical Engineering, 1990. - 288 p.

5. Ozel T., Altan T. Determination of workpiece flow stress and friction at the chip-tool contact for high-speed cutting // Int. J. of Machine Tools & Manufacture. v. 40, 2000, pp. 133–152.

6. Mahfoudi F., List G., Molinari A., Moufki A., Boulanouar L. High speed turning for hard material with PCBN inserts: tool wear analysis// Int. J. Machining and Machinability of Materials, Vol. 3 Nos. 1/2, 2008, pp. 62–79.

7. Khamidullova, L.R. Classification and comprehensive assessment of lubricating fluids according to the degree of impact on humans and the biosphere /L.R. Khamidullova, A.V. Vasiliev // Proceedings of the Samara Scientific Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences. - 2011. - T. 13. - No. 5. - S. 279-281.

8. Kamenskaya A.A. The impact of metal processing industries by cutting machine-building enterprises on the environment and ways to reduce the damage caused: Analyt. review / A.A. Kamenskaya, R.I. Kovalova, V.M. Labetsky // State Public Scientific and Technical Library of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences; Alt. polytechnic in-t - Novosibirsk: State Public Scientific and Technical Library of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 1992. - 102 p.

9. Afanasiev S.V. Technological aspects of cleaning metal chips from coolant: / Afanasyev S.V., Tatarinova A.D. "Chemical Engineering", August 2019. Access code: <https://chemtech.ru> Technologies

10. Dyakonov O.M. Dehydration and deoiling of metal shavings. Casting and metallurgy. 2011. No. 3S. P.186 - 191.

11. E.M. Rubio, B. Agustina, M. Marín, A. Bericua. Cooling Systems Based on Cold Compressed Air / Procedia Engineering 132 (2015) p. 413-418.

12. Kurnosov, N. E., Lebedinskii, K. V., Asoskov, A. S., Lebedinskii, K. V., Asoskov, A. S., Provision of cutting tool cooling in machine building by a system for

supplying cooled ionized air to the cutting zone, Izvestiya Vysshikh Uchebnykh Zavedenii. Volga region. Technical science. - 2017. - No. 4 (44). - S. 68-80. DOI 10.21685/2072-3059-2017-4-7.

13. Vylegzhanin D.G. The use of air cooling systems in the processing of metals by cutting // Sixth All-Russian Conference of Young Scientists and Specialists. Collection of works. Moscow, September 25-28, 2013 - М.: MSTU im. N.E. Bauman, 2013 .S. 45-46.

14. Pat 204216 U1 Ros. Federation, IPC B23B 27/10 (2006.01) Metalworking tools with cooling.

15. Pat 209971 U1 Ros. Federation, IPC B23B 27/10 (2006.01) Air-cooled metalworking tools.

16. Protodyakonov M. M. Methods of rational planning of experiments / M. M. Protodyakonov, R. I. Teder. – М.: Science. 1970, - 76 p.

17. Y. L. Liberman, S. V. Lukinskikh and A. V. Smirnov. Study of the influence of the design of the turning tool on the removal of thermal energy from the cutting zone / IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng. 966 012124

ОЦЕНКА ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ШУМА НА ЧЕЛОВЕКА И ОКРУЖАЮЩУЮ СРЕДУ

Мирзахамдамов Ж.К.

Ассистент,

Андижанский машиностроительный институт

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF NOISE ON HUMANS AND THE ENVIRONMENT

Mirzakhamdorov J.

Assistant,

Andijan Machine-Building Institute

Аннотация

Известно, что шум – это совокупность звуков, которые мешают человеку работать или отдыхать, вызывают акустический дискомфорт, оказывают пагубное влияние на здоровье человека и окружающую среду. Рассматриваются результаты экспериментальных исследований по оценке загрязненности атмосферного воздуха автомобильным шумовым источником.

Abstract

It is known that noise is a set of sounds that interfere with a person's work or rest, cause acoustic discomfort, and have a detrimental effect on human health and the environment.

Ключевые слова: Транспортный шум, транспортный поток, ДВС, дорожное покрытие, гипертонический шум. Транспортный поток, автомобильный двигатель, дорожное покрытие, гипертонический шум.

Keywords: Traffic noise, traffic flow, engine, road surface, hypertonic.

ВВЕДЕНИЕ.

По данным Всемирной организации здравоохранения (ВОЗ), шумовое загрязнение является одной из самых опасных экологических угроз для здоровья человека [1].

По данным Европейского агентства по окружающей среде, только шумовое загрязнение в Европе является одной из основных причин смерти людей и ежегодно уносит жизни 16,6 тыс. человек. В связи с этим во многих странах мира проводятся научно-исследовательские работы по снижению уровня автотранспортных шумовых загрязнений. На рис.1 представлены основные источники шумовых загрязнений атмосферы, откуда видно, что главным

источником является транспортная система. Автомобили вносят свой вклад в акустическое загрязнение современных городов, и оно растет. В основном это нарушение потока транспортного шума в населенных пунктах. Шум средней и низкой частоты в основном исходит от транспортных средств. Водители и находящиеся в транспортных средствах также подвергаются воздействию шума. В последние годы, учитывая неуклонный рост автопарка, в частности количества автомобилей, негативное влияние людей на шум дорожного движения усиливается.